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D6.1 Secondary phenotyping analysis of 15 mouse models

Compiled by:

Asrar Ali Khan, INFRAFRONTIER GmbH

Input and TA data from:

Helmut Fuchs, Helmholtz Zentrum München GmbH (German Mouse Clinic, GMC)

Jan Rozman, Czech Centre for Phenogenomics (CCP)

Mohammed Selloum and Tania Sorg, CERBM-GIE (ICS Mouse Clinical Institute)

Ana Zarubica, INSERM-CIPHE

Maria Denis, Biomedcode

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Introduction

This report compiles information about the secondary phenotyping trans-national access (TNA) calls i.e., call overview, selected user projects, outcomes and outlook.

The main service providers involved were:

- Helmholtz Zentrum München GmbH (German Mouse Clinic, GMC)
- Institute of Molecular Genetics of the ASCR, v.v.i., Czech Centre for Phenogenomics (CCP)
- Centre Européen de Recherche en Biologie et Médecine - Groupement d'Intérêt Economique CERBM-GIE (ICS Mouse Clinical Institute)
- INSERM-CIPHE
- Biomedcode Hellas SA

The WP6 partners are four independently operating European mouse clinics that have an outstanding track record of scientific achievement and successful collaborative work as demonstrated in the EC funded EUMORPHIA and EUMODIC projects. All partners are founding members of the International Mouse Phenotyping Consortium (IMPC). The participating infrastructures offer access to unique resources and expertise provided by the world leading mouse clinics. Each center is fully equipped with state-of-the-art research instrumentation to facilitate comprehensive and secondary specialised phenotypic analyses covering a wide range of physiological functions including cardiovascular, neuro-behavior and metabolism, and detailed expert pathology assessments. All phenotyping activities are routinely performed in a high- throughput capacity, as a service to support internal programs or for the wider scientific community on a fee-for-service or a collaborative basis. Biomedcode is a Contract Research Organization (CRO) providing full preclinical drug evaluation services using a unique collection of proprietary mouse models of human inflammatory diseases. They are equipped with several standard induced models of inflammatory diseases and uses advanced platforms for comprehensive phenotyping of disease progression.

Call Overview

Four specialised phenotyping calls were run until June 2019. A first call with a focus on behavioural phenotyping was released in November 2018, and a further call focussing on metabolic phenotyping in March 2019. The main objective of these INFRAFRONTIER2020 Trans-national Access call was to facilitate widespread access to the unique infrastructure and scientific expertise of the participating INFRAFRONTIER mouse clinics, where mouse mutant lines can be tested through specialised, disease focussed phenotyping pipelines.

Disturbed energy balance regulation results in obesity and in numerous related metabolic disorders such as type 2 diabetes mellitus. In this call, INFRAFRONTIER mouse clinics offered access to specialised phenotyping pipelines comprising of state-of-the-art test assays monitoring disease related parameters. In-depth behavioural phenotyping supports the elucidation of the molecular and genetic basis of behavioural impairments that are relevant for human neuropsychiatric disorders such as anxiety disorders, post-traumatic stress

disorder, depression, schizophrenia, autism, attention-deficit hyperactivity disorder, Parkinson's and Alzheimer's Disease.

Access to mouse clinics was granted based on scientific excellence and supported the development and in-depth characterisation of mouse models for investigating gene function and human pathophysiology. INFRAFRONTIER will provide open access to all characterised disease models and phenotyping data. In these first calls, six phenotyping projects were supported. Two subsequent calls with a focus on behavioural-, functional immune-phenotyping screen by mass cytometry, and on induced secondary phenotyping screen under acute or more chronic inflammatory conditions were released in spring 2019.

A total of 28 proposals from 13 different countries were submitted in response to the four calls (9 behaviour, 7 metabolism, 6 for neurology / behaviour, and 6 for immuno-phenotyping and inflammation) and a total of 14 calls were selected. A mixed panel of members of INFRAFRONTIER and of an external Evaluation Committee assessed service requests supported by the TA activity. In addition to scientific merit of applicants, soundness of the proposal and research plans, and the beneficial impact of the proposed novel mouse line on the wider biomedical research community was evaluated. Applicants were informed on the outcome of the evaluation within 6 weeks after the end of the call. All applications were handled with strict confidentiality.

Geographic origin of submitted WP6 proposals

TA call website:

Call 1 Metabolic and behavioural phenotyping: <https://www.infrafrontier.eu/specialised-phenotyping-metabolic-and-behavioral-phenotyping-pipelines>

Call 2 Immuno-phenotyping and inflammation: <https://www.infrafrontier.eu/specialised-phenotyping>

Total number of applications: 32

Selected user projects: 15

Gender distribution: 74% male; 26% female

Research area / disease / syndrome covered in selected secondary phenotyping projects:

- Thyroid disorders
- Human aggrecanopathies
- Brain size and connectivity
- Neuromuscular functions
- Alterations in behaviour and impaired cognition
- Alterations in immune responses
- Neurocognitive disorders due to viral infections during pregnancies
- Skeletal muscle-initiated crosstalk with other tissues
- Ataxia and hearing loss

Selected User Projects

Selected specialised phenotyping projects (behavioral phenotyping):

Production centre	Applicant	Project scope
PHENOMIN-ICS Partner 5	Godin France, IGBMC (Institut de Génétique et de Biologie Moléculaire et Cellulaire), Strasbourg	<p>KIF21B as a major locus for neurodevelopmental disorders</p> <p>Kinesin motor proteins play a fundamental role for normal neuronal development by controlling intracellular cargo transport and microtubule cytoskeleton organization in both axons and dendrites. Kinesin mis-regulation often leads to severe human neurodevelopmental disorders, suggesting a key role of the kinesin superfamily in brain development.</p> <p>In the proposed project, our specific objectives are first to uncover the mechanisms by which KIF21B regulates brain size and connectivity and second to determine how those defects contribute to the cognitive and motor clinical manifestations in the KIF21B patients. As our preliminary data strongly indicate that Tm1a KO faithfully models neuroanatomical anomalies observed in patients, we will use this Kif21b constitutive knockout model to perform behavioral and neuroanatomical studies, as well as molecular studies. Clinical phenotypes of patients with mutations in KIF21B include microcephaly, CC agenesis, intellectual disability and epilepsy. Some of the proposed tests corresponding to the global phenotyping are appropriate to assess consequences of KIF21B loss of function on motor, behavioral abilities, as well as susceptibility to epilepsy.</p> <p>Success of this project will be of major importance for human health, as it will significantly increase our understanding of the molecular and cellular causes of the neurodevelopmental disorders associated with kinesin dysfunction. In the long term, microtubule-related pathways may represent new targets for therapeutic approaches.</p>

<p>PHENOMIN-ICS Partner 5</p>	<p>Laporte France, IGBMC (Institut de Génétique et de Biologie Moléculaire et Cellulaire), Strasbourg</p>	<p>Understand the role of Dynamin 2 in nerve, muscle and other physiological functions</p> <p>Dynamin 2 is a ubiquitously expressed large GTPase implicated in many cellular processes ranging from cytoskeleton regulation to membrane remodelling and endocytosis. Heterozygous mutations of dynamin 2 have been associated to diseases such as Charcot Marie Tooth peripheral neuropathy and Centronuclear Myopathy. Owing to the pleiotropic physiological functions of DNM2 and its strong involvement in neuromuscular functions, we propose a wide phenotyping of a knock-in line harboring a specific patient mutation.</p> <p>Our preliminary data on motor function and muscle force analysis showed a muscle weakness and an abnormal nerve stimulation leading to an irregular muscle contraction. Abnormal neuromuscular junctions were noted, suggesting this mouse line display a mix between CMT neuropathy and CNM myopathy. Thus, an in-depth phenotyping would potentially reveal the pleiotropic impact of this common mutation. Previous work has only been limited to study the effect of dynamin 2 on nerve and muscle phenotypes independently The study of the effect of Dnm2 S619L will help to decipher its implication in muscle and nerve physiology and will shed light on dynamin 2's role both for health and disease.</p>
<p>PHENOMIN-ICS Partner 5</p>	<p>Frederico UK, Francis Crick Institute</p>	<p>Examine whether Flt3L-deficient mice have any alterations in behaviour and cognition</p> <p>Historically, the nervous and immune systems have been treated as two separate and nonoverlapping entities. Neuroscientists have focused their efforts in understanding which neural pathways command complex features of behaviour or memory whilst immunologists have concentrated in the elucidation of the principles underlying initiation and regulation of immune responses. However, it is now clear that an intense communication exists between these two systems mediated by common molecular signalling cues, such as cytokines and neurotransmitters.</p> <p>Given that antigen specificity is at the heart of precognitive T cell meningeal homing and function, we have reasoned that dendritic cell (DC)-deficient mice would also show impaired cognition. DCs express FMS-like tyrosine kinase (Flt3) and strictly rely on FMS-like tyrosine kinase 3 ligand (Flt3L) for their development and maintenance. Thus, Flt3L^{-/-} mice are essentially DC-deficient. Although this genetic model has been key for the elucidation of DC mediated roles during immune responses, whether DCs play a role in on-immune functions is completely unexplored. We have generated preliminary data that show that conventional dendritic cell subsets reside in the meningeal compartment and require Flt3L for their development. Furthermore, using a DC lineage labelling approach⁸ we have further</p>

		demonstrated that DCs inhabit the meningeal compartment of healthy mice. Therefore, we would like to examine whether Flt3L-deficient mice have any alterations in behaviour and cognition.
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Selected specialised phenotyping projects (metabolic):

Production centre	Applicant	Project scope
CCP Partner 3	Kero Finland, University of Turku	<p>Thyroid disorders (hypothyroidism, hyperthyroidism and thyroid tumors) are common diseases affecting more than 200 million people worldwide. In human, they are essential for adult health, childhood brain and growth development. Furthermore, even minute alterations from the normal range in thyroid hormone levels may be associated with an elevated risk of cardiovascular morbidity and mortality, dyslipidemia, obesity, fracture risk and lifetime cancer (2). Thyroid hormones are also key metabolic regulators coordinating short-term and long-term energy needs. The general effects of thyroid hormones on metabolism has been studied in several animal models and in human up to one-third of patients with type 1 diabetes (T1DM) have also thyroid disease.</p> <p>Applicant has generated the first nonautoimmune knockin model for hyperthyroidism. This knockin mouse model carries the patient-derived constitutively active thyrotropin receptor (TSHR) mutation D633H and leads to hyperthyroidism.</p> <p>Here we propose a new study evaluating the metabolic adaptation in hyperthyroidism in more detail. This could help to understand more detail of the effect of TH on growth, glucose-, and lipid metabolism and weight gain.</p>
CCP Partner 3	Petersen Austria, Medical University of Vienna	<p>Using publically available single cell sequencing analysis of the neural tube together with an evolution approach we tried to identify novel genes involved in metabolism. Interestingly enough, only one uncharacterised protein showed a positive correlation between these two. Namely 1700011H14RIK/CCDC198 in mice and C14ORF105 in humans</p> <p>Knock out mice do not have any visual phenotypes. However, a number of abnormalities related to metabolic dysfunction such as increased weight and decreased energy expenditure develop.</p>

		Only young female mice (3 months old) have been analyzed. The project therefore would greatly benefit from additional phenotyping from males and females at a later stage.
CCP Partner 3	Potter Oxford Brookes University	<p>As part of a forward genetics screen for age-related phenotypes we have identified a point mutation in the C lectin binding domain of aggrecan, Acan5837C>T resulting in an A1496V change, which exhibited abnormal growth and accelerated joint disease. This is the first viable homozygous mutation, which closely resembles phenotypes observed in human aggrecanopathies.</p> <p>In addition to the joint disease observed in these mice there was a significant difference in body composition obesity and qualitative differences in adipose tissue. Whilst the applicant has preliminary evidence for a role of aggrecan in the metabolism in these mutant mice the preliminary screening was limited, and more comprehensive phenotyping data are needed.</p>

Selected specialised phenotyping projects (neurology / behaviour):

Production centre	Applicant	Project scope
HMGU / GMC Partner 2	Delezie Switzerland, University of Basel	<p>Skeletal muscle-initiated crosstalk with other tissues accomplished through the secretion of myokines. The release of myokines by contracting muscle cells exerts broad effects on functions such as neuroplasticity, mood and memory. The applicant's lab is studying the contribution of circadian clock components to muscle and whole-body physiology. They have generated mice expressing Cre under the control of the human skeletal actin (HAS) promoter and crossed it with mice carrying a floxed Rora allele (Muscle Knock-Out MKO). Using this model they have identified novel pathways by which the circadian clock regulates metabolism in skeletal muscle. The mice show a severe decrease in spontaneous locomotion and a unique behavioral phenotype. Aim is to analyze this mouse model in depth in the German Mouse Clinic to assess stress, depression and anxiety.</p> <p>The study could reveal a novel and extremely surprising link between the muscle clock and motivation to perform physical activity.</p>

HMGU / GMC Partner 2	Forsythe UK, University of Leicester	The applicant is investigating the molecular mechanisms underlying information transmission in the brain with a focus on the auditory pathway, hearing loss and the role of ion channel genes. There are more than 80 genes for potassium channel subunits. Kv3 potassium channels are widely expressed in the brain but only Kv3.1 and Kv3.3 (KCNC3) are expressed in the auditory brainstem. Data from human studies have demonstrated that a cohort suffering from ataxia possess a point mutation in the Kv3.3 subunit. A humanized mouse model recapitulating this mutation was produced using CRISPR/Cas9 genome editing. The line shows mild tremors and some degree of ataxia. A full behavioural phenotyping in the GMC will be highly advantageous as part of the applicant's lab broader study of Kv3.3 function.
HMGU / GMC Partner 2	Gabriel Germany, Leibniz Institute for Experimental Virology, Hamburg	Viral infections during pregnancy and impact on offspring e.g., the risk to develop neurocognitive disorders in later life. The applicant has developed a mouse model that mimics human pregnancies in terms of maternal immune tolerance to maintain the allogenic fetus. Preliminary data suggest that offspring born to IAV infected mothers might suffer from long-term neurocognitive disorders. Thus, the neurology and behavior pipeline of the GMC provides an invaluable opportunity to thoroughly assess offspring from IAV infected mothers.

Selected specialised phenotyping projects (inflammation / immune phenotyping):

Production centre	Applicant	Project scope
BIOMEDCODE Partner 20	Boehm, France, IGBMC Strasbourg	Study the role of Ca ²⁺ imbalance, caused by the Stim1 ^{R340W/+} mutation, in LPS challenge and psoriasis pathology. Stim1R304W/+ knock-in mouse model harbors the most recurrent STIM1 GOF mutation R304W. These mice recapitulate the main clinical features of the human pathology TAM/STRMK syndrom (tubular aggregate myopathy, TAM and Stormorken syndrome,

		<p>STRMK), while they have also shown evidence of dysregulation of the immune system, that could be correlated to some human patient condition.</p> <p>The project aimed to further explore the role of STIM1 mutation and the physiological impact of Ca²⁺ imbalance through a secondary phenotyping screen of the Stim1R304W/+ mice under acute and chronic inflammatory conditions. Regarding the phenotype of the Stim1R304W/+ mice the Lipopolysaccharide (LPS) Induced Cytokine cascade and IMQ-induced psoriasis were investigated in this mouse model.</p>
BIOMEDCODE Partner 20	Schneider, Germany, University of Erlangen	<p>Response of Atf2^{ΔEC/ΔEC} mice to LPS challenge.</p> <p>Comparison of the TNBS induced colitis pathology development in Atf2^{ΔEC/ΔEC} versus Atf2^{+/+} mice.</p> <p>The activating transcription factor 2 (ATF2) is a cancer gene chameleon that can act as tumor suppressor or oncogene in a context- and stimulus dependent manner. As a member of the activator protein 1 (AP1) transcription factor family, ATF2 is involved in many hallmarks of cancer such as proliferation, apoptosis, repair, invasion, or inflammation.</p> <p>Using Atf2^{ΔIEC/ΔIEC} mice that specifically have lost ATF2 in the epithelium, the hypothesis that ATF2 is protecting the intestinal epithelium from inflammation or is promoting healing of injured mucosa was tested. A combination of LPS-induced cytokine cascade (acute model) and the TNBS-colitis (disease model) was chosen as the best approach.</p>
BIOMEDCODE Partner 20	Raemet , University of Tampere, Finland	<p>Response of Nhlrc2^{FINCA/-} mice to LPS challenge.</p> <p>Comparison of the EAE pathology development in Nhlrc2^{FINCA/-} versus wt mice.</p> <p>NHL-repeat containing protein 2 (NHLRC2) is an essential cytosolic protein of undetermined function, mutations were recently by the project leader to be associated with a novel human disease named as FINCA (fibrosis, neurodegeneration, cerebral angiomas). FINCA is defined as an early-onset multi-organ condition, predominantly characterized by severe interstitial pulmonary fibrosis, progressive neurodegeneration, anemia and recurrent infections.</p> <p>NHLRC2 is widely expressed in human and mouse tissues. Nhlrc2^{FINCA/-} mice are heterozygous for NHLRC2 knockout and for a knock-in FINCA mutant, c.G442T; p.Asp148Tyr. Nhlrc2^{FINCA/-} mice show normal growth compared to their wild-type litter mates and do not develop a severe disease phenotype as described in FINCA patients. Taking into account that FINCA patients suffer from severe recurrent infections, environmental factors such as</p>

		<p>pathogens may play an additional role in triggering a more severe outcome of this lethal disease. <i>Nhlrc2</i>^{FINCA/-} mice, housed in specific pathogen-free conditions, may have lacked an immunological component important for the FINCA disease onset. Therefore, to study acute exposure to endotoxins, LPS-induced cytokine cascade, was performed, to allow comparison of responses of mutant and normal mice, while Experimental Autoimmune Encephalomyelitis (EAE) was performed, in reference to neurodegenerative events observed in human patients, to allow the evaluation of the effect of the mutation on an induced neurodegenerative pathology.</p>
INSERM-CIPHE	Naquet France, Centre d'Immunologie de Marseille Luminy	<p>Vnn1 pantetheinase</p> <p>Aggressive soft tissue sarcomas (STS) display an enhanced glycolytic profile to optimize their growth and escape immune responses. The applicant identified Vnn1 as a tumor suppressor in sarcoma, supported by observations in humans. Vnn1 regulates homeostasis of coenzyme A stores and mitochondrial activity while limiting glycolysis. These autocrine and paracrine effects maintain tumor differentiation, restrain growth and are associated with a status of immune activation. The latter observation is the basis of the submitted proposal. Objective of the project is to inject C57BL/6 female mice (8-10 weeks) subcutaneously with Vnn1-deficient sarcoma cells to evaluate the functional phenotype of tumor infiltrating lymphocytes TILs on day 15 post graft by mass cytometry. This analysis should provide a precise estimation of the impact of Vnn1 enzymatic activity within an aggressive STS on the functional potential of TILs as defined by the CIPHE secondary functional immune-phenotyping.</p>
INSERM-CIPHE	Lawrence UK, King's College London	<p>Ube2n</p> <p>While the mechanisms of TLR-induced dendritic cell (DC) maturation are well characterized, we still understand little about the signaling pathways and upstream regulators that drive steady-state DC maturation. Recent studies suggest that genes, which regulate the NF-κB signaling pathway, play critical roles in restraining DC maturation in steady-state. In the absence of such factors, steady-state DC maturation becomes immunostimulatory, leading to inappropriate priming of naïve T cells and auto-immunity. For example, targeted deletion of <i>Tnfrsf3</i> in DC, using CD11c-Cre transgenic mice, led to marked splenomegaly and lymphadenopathy within 3 weeks of birth associated with the accumulation of large</p>

		<p>numbers of myeloid and lymphoid cells ¹. Tnfrsf3 was shown to restrict MyD88-dependent signals that drive DC activation and subsequent T-cell expansion. We recently showed that the kinase IKKβ (encoded by the <i>Ikkβ</i> gene) plays a similar role on the restriction of DC activation in steady-state ², again targeted deletion of <i>Ikkβ</i> in DC using CD11c-cre mice led to a spontaneous autoimmune phenotype due to loss of T regulatory cells that restrict T cell activation against self-antigens in the periphery.</p> <p>This project will explore the role of the ubiquitin-conjugating enzyme Ubc13 (Ube2n) in DC activation, since Ubc13 is a critical regulator of the NF-κB pathway.</p> <p>The UBE2V1-UBE2N and UBE2V2-UBE2N heterodimers catalyze the synthesis of non-canonical K63-linked polyubiquitin chains. This type of polyubiquitination does not lead to protein degradation by the proteasome but instead creates scaffolds for signal transduction. K63-linked polyubiquitin chains are critical for activation of the MAP3K7/TAK1 complex which in turn results in the activation of NF-κB and MAPK pathways. The role of K63-mediated signalling in DC through targeting of Ubc13/Ube2n has not yet been studied. We have generated conditional knockout mice for Ube2n in DC using CD11c-cre crossed with Ube2n floxed mice. Our hypothesis is these mice will develop spontaneous autoimmunity due to increased DC activation and subsequent activation of autoreactive T cells. In Our preliminary analysis of DC-specific Ube2n mutant mice, we have observed splenomegaly and lymph node adenopathy, in support of this hypothesis.</p> <p>We propose here to perform a deep immunophenotyping of DC-specific Ube2n mutant mice and littermate controls to fully characterise the impact of this mutation on immune homeostasis.</p>
INSERM-CIPHE	Loretta Tuosto Italy, Sapienza University, Rome	<p>Cd28</p> <p>CD28 is the prototypical and best-characterized costimulatory molecule on T cells (for review. CD28 signals play a role for optimal naive T cell activation, cytokine production, proliferation, and survival. CD28 is critical for regulatory T cell survival and the maintenance of immune homeostasis. In summary, the CD28 costimulatory signals modulate the function of both effector T cells and Treg cells. Previously, we investigated the role of the CD28 molecule in inflammation events such as in multiple sclerosis and we analyzed also the behavior of this molecule in mouse biological systems. The large majority of immune</p>

		<p>responses described using mice are analyzed between eight and 12 weeks. In this age range, many developmental processes are ongoing, and changes in physiology with age may have a large impact on experimental variables (for example: peak bone mass and B cell turnover are not reached until around 26 weeks of age in rodents). It could be important to revisit some aspects of immunology on these older animals and in this project; we will focus on <i>Cd28</i>-deficient mice (C57BL/6J background). In collaboration, we are analyzing tumor responses in immunocompetent animals by measuring the tumor growth upon orthotopic breast tumor (EO771 cell line) injection in mammary glands. Both effector T cells and Tregs play a role in the control of tumor progression in this model: CD8+ T cells and Tregs as depletion of CD4+CD25+FoxP3+ Tregs using PC61 mAb (CD25 mAb), abolishes tumor growth (Colisson R., personal communication). Initial measurements of tumor growth in <i>Cd28</i>-deficient mice of eight to 12 weeks in different tumor models did not reveal a critical role for CD28. Here, we performed these experiments in WT versus <i>Cd28</i>-deficient mice of eight or 24 weeks of age. Indeed, in mice at eight weeks, they are no major difference for tumor growth between WT and <i>Cd28</i>-deficient mice. However, with age the tumor progression slows down in WT mice and even more impressive in <i>Cd28</i>-deficient genotype as the tumor disappears completely.</p> <p>In this proposal, it will be important to analyze the intratumoral CD45+ cells at day #11 post-injection. The suggestion will be to include 12 individual age- matched (24 weeks) mice upon EO771 tumor challenge (11 days) split in two conditions (C57BL/6J vs CD28 KO). Taking in account that CD28 can be expressed in many immune cell types, largely involved in Treg homeostasis wit might be a role in CCR8+ intratumoral Tregs and/or in aged Tregs, it will be important to get a large Treg profile inside the intratumoral immune landscape.</p>
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Outcomes

Researcher Name	User Project	Short Name	Status	Remarks
Johann Boehm	Stim1	BMC	Completed	
Regine Schneider	Atf2	BMC	Completed	
Mika Raemet	Nhlrc2	BMC	Completed	

Philippe Naquet	Vnn1	CIPHE	Completed	
Loretta Tuosto	Cd28	CIPHE	Delayed	Will be finalised by the end of the year
Toby Lawrence	Ube2n	CIPHE	Completed	
Julien Delezie	MKO	HMGU	Completed	
Ian Forsythe	KCNC3	HMGU	Completed	
Guelsah Gabriel	IAVInfect	HMGU	Completed	
Bruno Frederico	Flt3L	ICS	Cancelled	Due to COVID-19
Juliette Godin	KIF21B	ICS	Completed	
Jocelyne Laporte	Dynamin	ICS	Completed	
Paul Potter	Aggrecan	IMG	Completed	
Jukka Kero	Thyroid Disorders	IMG	Completed	
Julian Petersen	C14ORF105	IMG	Completed	

User Feedback

User	Satisfied with the service?	Willingness to pay a competitive price (non-profit) for the same service you received under this open call?	Any publications being prepared?	Feedback Remarks
Juliette Godin	Yes	Maybe	Not yet	We are plenty satisfied of our collaboration with the ICS for the phenotyping of our mouse line of interest. I really appreciated their flexibility, meaning we adapted the pipeline to assess only the relevant phenotypes and analyzed not only

				the WT and hom as scheduled but also the heterozygous animals, as we suspected some mirror phenotype in these individuals. We received the final report at the due date and have been offered to discuss the results, that is very important.
Julien Delezie	Yes	Maybe	Yes	Amazing service provided by the German Mouse Clinic (Helmholtz Institute, Munich)! Thanks to all the scientists and administrative assistants involved in the project.

Feedback from Service Providers: Outlook, Hidden Costs and Problems

Metabolic phenotyping (CCP)

- In general, good experiences as a service provider. Proposals were scientifically sound and the communication with investigators was good
- CCP would be interested in future TA calls as an INFRAFRONTIER service in the field of metabolism, behavior, and embryonic phenotyping
- There were hidden costs due to the need to generate one new mutant line because of the mixed background of the initially suggested line

Behavioural phenotyping (ICS)

- General experience as a service provider:
 - Opportunities for further collaboration
 - Difficulties to manage breeding production with researcher
- Future and viability of the TA call as an INFRAFRONTIER service
 - Very important service for the research community
 - Propose TA as close as possible to the needs of the community (conduct a survey)
- Hidden costs
 - Additional cost (breeding and genotyping) in case of failure of cohort production (eg. sub-viability) due to the lack of zootechnical data
- Problems / Issues
 - COVID-19-related delays

Secondary functional immune-phenotyping screen by mass cytometry (CIPHE)

- Troubleshooting / Problems
 - Optimization of DC cell extraction (Lawrence, Ube2n)
 - In all projects, scientists requested panel adjustments from the one offered in the call. This required more time and work for optimising experimental conditions and panel validation
 - Major delay: Mouse line abolishment (Tuosoto, Cd28) due to COVID-19 pandemic
- Future and viability of the TA call as an INFRAFRONTIER service
 - Mass cytometry is still very much considered by scientists as a discovery tool requiring adjustment of markers to their own project
- Hidden costs
 - Setup experiments, adjustment and design of specific reagents requested by lead researchers of the projects were not included in initial proposal
 - Recommendation
 - Budget should be increased, or number of service unit decreased for a similar amount of money to maintain sustainability

- Another option is to perform standardized mass cytometry panel as initially proposed and incorporate specific markers and adjustments on collaborative basis with researcher independent from the TA pipeline

Secondary phenotyping of induced inflammatory models (Biomedcode)

- General experience as a service provider:
 - Positive experience. Excellent communication with the investigators.
 - Motivation to expand our services to include the phenotyping of mice imported from other facilities
 - Opportunities for further collaborations
- Troubleshooting / Problems (if any)
 - Difficulty to attract projects because of the specificity of the services offered and because we were not allowed to accommodate national requests.
 - Compromised health status of the mice resulting either in 1) delays of the importation of the mice due to the time required to treat the infections in the researchers' institutes or 2) extra arrangements from our side required to modify our mouse hosting conditions to avoid the spread of putative infections in our animal facility.
 - Shipping delays and cancellations due to COVID-19 resulting in upsets of the whole company's experimental schedule.
- Hidden Costs
 - Shifts in the company's schedule to handle shipment cancellations
 - Additional decontamination of our animal facilities
 - Consultation services
- Future and Viability
 - If there is a continued interest, we will need to invest in appropriately arranging and equipping (ventilated racks, IVCs) our animal facilities to be able to better accommodate imported mice.

Stand-alone dedicated INFRAFRONTIER service

This TA service encompassed a wide range of specialised secondary phenotyping services with varied outlooks and issues. For example, the inflammatory phenotyping offered by Biomedcode is a very specific service and as a result, it was difficult to find appropriate and feasible user projects. While the immune-phenotyping screen using mass spectroscopy offered by CIPHE was subject to extensive customisation based on user requests. Careful consideration and planning would be required to convert these pilot services into full-fledged INFRAFRONTIER services by accurately outlining the offered service, defining quality standards and mitigating hidden costs. A dedicated INFRAFRONTIER Services Working Group could be useful in this regard.

Unfortunately, the COVID-19 pandemic also led to the cancellation of one project and delayed three projects. Overall, users were satisfied with the services provided and direct feedback received from two users suggests that these services could be taken up on a fee-for-service basis.